

Design, synthesis and *in vitro* antibacterial studies of some biologically significant *N*-3-chloro-4-[2'-hydroxy-5'-(phenylazo)phenyl]azetid-2-ones

Anand K. Halve*, Deepti Bhadauria, Bhuwan Bhaskar, Rakesh Dubey and Raman Bhadauria

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : drhalve_chemjiwaji@rediffmail.com, dipti_1706@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 28 February 2006, revised 13 September 2006, accepted 29 November 2006

Abstract : The title compounds **3a-h** were prepared via the reaction of imine derivatives viz. substituted 2-hydroxy-5-(4'-nitrophenylazo)benzylidene anilines **2a-h** with ketenes generated by the reaction of chloroacetylchloride with triethylamine in 1,4-dioxane. The structures of synthesized compounds were assigned by elemental analysis and IR and ¹H NMR spectral datas. All the synthesized azetid-2-ones **3a-h** were assayed for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against several Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial pathogens. Some of the compounds have shown marginal activity.

Keywords : Azetid-2-ones, ketene-imines, antibacterials, *B. anthresis*.

The development of bacterial resistance to existing drugs is a major problem in antibacterial therapy and necessitates continuing research into new classes of antibacterials¹. β-Lactams (azetid-2-ones) are known to be of high clinical importance²⁻⁵ owing to their diverse biological applications as potent antibacterial⁶⁻⁸, antifungal⁹, antitubercular¹⁰, anticancer^{11,12}, anti-HIV¹³ agents and immunomodifier properties¹⁴. Besides, the ever-growing new applications of these products in the field ranging from enzyme-inhibition¹⁵⁻¹⁷ to the use of azetid-2-ones as starting materials¹⁸⁻²⁰ make this class of compounds as an attractive target for drug development. Following our interest in the reactivity of β-lactam nucleus and in continuation of our earlier studies²¹, herein we describe the synthesis of a new series of azetid-2-ones via [2+2] Staudinger reaction²²⁻²⁴ and their *in vitro* antibacterial efficacy against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial pathogens.

Results and discussion

The general synthetic strategy is summarized in Scheme 1. Substituted 2-hydroxy-5-(4'-nitrophenylazo)benzylidene anilines **2a-d** and 2-hydroxy-5-(4'-methoxyphenylazo)benzylidene anilines **2e-h** were synthesized by the treatment of various primary aromatic amines with 2-hydroxy-5-(4'-nitrophenylazo)benzene carbaldehyde **1a** and 2-hydroxy-5-(4'-methoxyphenylazo)benzene carbaldehyde **1b** in excess of ethanol. Further, cycloaddition of ketenes generated by the reaction of chloroacetylchloride with

triethylamine in 1,4-dioxane, on the imine component of compounds **2a-h** afforded the desired *N*-substituted-3-chloro-4-[2'-hydroxy-5'-(phenylazo)phenyl]azetid-2-ones **3a-h** in good yield. 2-Hydroxy-5-(4'-nitrophenylazo)benzene carbaldehyde **1a** and 2-hydroxy-5-(4'-methoxyphenylazo)benzene carbaldehyde **1b** were prepared by using reported methodology²⁵. The constitutions of all the products have been assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, IR and ¹H NMR spectral datas.

Antibacterial screening :

All the synthesized azetid-2-ones **3a-h** were screened for antibacterial activity against a panel of susceptible and resistant Gram-positive and Gram-negative organisms viz. *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus anthresis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* by disc-diffusion assay²⁶ at 500 μg/ml concentration. Standard drug - Chloromycetin was tested in the similar manner in order to compare the relative activity of compounds with that of standard. The antibacterial data of tested compounds are presented in Table 1. The potencies followed the order 4'''-chloro derivatives (**3b** and **3f**) >> 4''-nitro derivatives (**3a**, **3c** and **3d**) > 4''-methoxy derivatives (**3e**, **3h** and **3g**). The two compounds **3b** and **3f** showed best *in vitro* antibacterial activity against, *S. aureus* and *B. anthresis* and also exhibited marked inhibition against *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*. Amongst the nitro derivatives, compound **3a** with an unsubstituted benzylidene moiety, displayed a

Scheme 1

Table 1. Antibacterial activity (zone of inhibition in mm^a) of azetidin-2-ones 3a-h

Compd.	Gram-positive microorganisms		Gram-negative microorganisms	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. anthresis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>
3a	12	33	8	11
3b	36	32	12	20
3c	8	-	-	10
3d	-	-	-	8
3e	25	18	8	17
3f	33	25	8	12
3g	12	8	-	-
3h	22	16	-	14
Chloromycetin	42	40	24	35

^aControl DMF = No activity. Both test compounds and standard were tested at 500 µg/ml.

high degree of antibacterial activity against *B. anthresis*. Further, it has been observed that 4'''-bromo and 4'''-methoxy substitutions resulted in a marked reduction in

the antibacterial activity of compounds 3c and 3d. However, among methoxy derivatives it was observed that compound 3e, 3g and 3h showed significant antibacterial activity particularly against Gram-positive pathogens viz. *S. aureus* and *B. anthresis*.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds (2a-h) and (3a-h) were routinely monitored by TLC and purified by column chromatography using acetone/*n*-hexane (1 : 3); (2 : 3) as a mobile phase and silica gel-G (200-400 mesh); (60-200 mesh) as a stationary phase, respectively. FT-IR spectra were scanned on Shimadzu prestige-21 instrument in KBr disk. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-390 MHz spectrometer in DMSO-*d*₆ using TMS as an internal standard, chemical shift in δ ppm. Elemental analysis was performed on Carlo Erba 1108 analyzer.

Synthesis of 2-hydroxy-5-(4'-nitrophenylazo)-4''-chlorobenzylidene aniline 2b : A mixture of 2-hydroxy-

5-(4'-nitrophenylazo)benzene carbaldehyde **1a** (0.001 mol) and 4-chloro aniline (0.001 mol) in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and a drop of conc. sulphuric acid was added. The separated solid was filtered under suction, washed and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 68%; m.p. 110 °C; IR (KBr) 3548 (O-H), 1652 (C=N), 1590 (N=N), 1483 (N=O, asym.), 1343 cm⁻¹ (N=O, sym.); ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.48 (1H, s, OH), 9.78 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.2–7.8 (11H, m, aromatic protons) (Found : C, 59.11; H, 3.01; N, 13.97. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₃O₃N₄Cl : C, 59.92; H, 3.41; N, 14.71 %).

Similarly other compounds were prepared **2a**, m.p. 187°; **c**, 162°; **d**, 205°; **e**, 188°; **f**, 156°; **g**, 210°; **h**, 190° in 60–68% yields. **2a** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.32 (1H, s, OH), 9.83 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.3–7.7 (12H, m, ArH), **2c** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.91 (1H, s, OH), 9.27 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.2–7.6 (11H, m, ArH), **2d** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.67 (1H, s, OH), 9.89 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.4–7.9 (11H, m, aromatic protons), **2e** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.35 (1H, s, OH), 9.38 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.5–8.0 (11H, m, aromatic protons), **2f** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.29 (1H, s, OH), 9.42 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.1–7.5 (11H, m, aromatic protons), **2g** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.86 (1H, s, OH), 9.82 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.4–7.9 (11H, m, aromatic protons), **2h** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.98 (1H, s, OH), 9.97 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6–7.9 (11H, m, aromatic protons).

Synthesis of N-4'''-chloro-3-chloro-4-[2'-hydroxy-5'-(4''-nitrophenylazo)phenyl]azetid-2-one 3b : Compound **2b** (0.001 mol) was added to a constantly stirred solution of triethylamine (0.001 mol) and chloroacetylchloride (0.001 mol) in 1,4-dioxane. The reaction mixture was mechanically stirred at 50 °C for half an hour. The reaction vessel was kept at room temperature for 30 min and refluxed for 8 h. On cooling, the precipitate was obtained, which was filtered thoroughly, washed with water and recrystallised from chloroform+methanol mixture, yield 62%; m.p. 172 °C; IR (KBr) 3473 (O-H), 1762 (C=O, characteristic of four membered rings), 1587 (N=N), 1453 (N=O, asym.), 1321 cm⁻¹ (N=O, sym.); ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.2 (1H, s, OH), 2.9 (1H, d, CH-N), 2.3 (1H, d, CH-Cl), 7.3–7.9 (11H, m, aromatic protons) (Found : C, 54.83; H, 2.91; N, 11.73. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₄O₄N₄Cl₂ : C, 55.14; H, 3.06; N, 12.25 %).

Similarly other compounds were prepared **3a**, m.p. 166°; **c**, 197°; **d**, 188°; **e**, 194°; **f**, 138°; **g**, 182°; **h**, 208° in 58–70% yields. **3a** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.9 (1H, s, OH), 2.7 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.4 Hz, CH-N), 2.1 (1H, d,

*J*_{3,4} 4.4 Hz, CH-Cl), 7.2–7.7 (12H, m, aromatic protons), **3c** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.6 (1H, s, OH), 2.89 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.4 Hz, CH-N), 2.23 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.4 Hz, CH-Cl), 7.1–7.8 (11H, m, aromatic protons), **3d** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.8 (1H, s, OH), 2.96 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.2 Hz, CH-N), 2.23 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.2 Hz, CH-Cl), 7.4–7.9 (11H, m, aromatic protons), **3e** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.12 (1H, s, OH), 2.73 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.7 Hz, CH-N), 2.13 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.7 Hz CH-Cl), 7.3–8.0 (12H, m, aromatic protons), **3f** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.73 (1H, s, OH), 2.96 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.4 Hz, CH-N), 7.2–7.6 (11H, m, aromatic protons), **3g** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.87 (1H, s, OH), 2.88 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.2 Hz, CH-N), 7.3–7.9 (11H, m, aromatic protons), **3h** : ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.67 (1H, s, OH), 2.94 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.6 Hz, CH-N), 2.16 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 4.6 Hz), 7.4–7.8 (11H, m, aromatic protons).

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to the Dean, Birla Institute of Medical Research and College of Life Sciences, Gwalior for providing facilities for antibacterial screening and to the UGC, New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. F. Reck, F. Zhou, M. Girardot, G. Kern, C. J. Eyermann, N. J. Hales, R. R. Ramsay and M. B. Granestock, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **48**, 499.
2. M. Feroci, J. Lessard, M. Orsini and A. Inesi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2005, **46**, 8517.
3. M. I. Page (ed.), "The Chemistry of β-Lactams", Blackie Academic and Professional, New York, 1992.
4. G. I. Georg (ed.), "The Organic Chemistry of β-Lactams", VCH Press, New York, 1993.
5. R. B. Morin and M. Gorman (ed.), "Chemistry and Biology of β-Lactam Antibiotics", Academic Press, New York, 1982, Vols. 1-3.
6. M. C. Sleeman, C. H. Mackinnon, K. S. Heuriton and C. J. Schofield, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2002, **12**, 597.
7. B. Alcaide and P. Almendros, *Curr. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **11**, 1921.
8. S. V. More, D. V. Dongarkhadekar, R. N. Chavan, W. N. Jadav, S. R. Busare and R. P. Pawar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 768.
9. J. S. Biradar and S. V. Modha, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 141.
10. R. P. Tripathi, N. Tiwari, N. Dwivedi and V. K. Tiwari, *Med. Res. Rev.*, 2005, **25**, 93.
11. B. K. Banik, F. F. Becker and I. Banik, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**, 2523.
12. I. Banik, F. F. Becker and B. K. Banik, *J. Med.*

- Chem.*, 2003, **46**, 12.
13. T. Sperka, J. Pitlik, P. Baghossi and J. Tozser, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2005, **15**, 3086.
14. S. S. Bari, S. Madan and M. K. Sethi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1999, **38**, 10.
15. J. W. Clader, *Curr. Top. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **5**, 243.
16. D. Ruhela, P. Chatterjee and R. A. Vishwakarma, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2005, **3**, 1043.
17. R. Moreiva, A. B. Santana, J. Iley, J. Neres, K. T. Douglas, P. N. Horton and M. B. Hursthouse, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **48**, 4861.
18. I. Ojima, S. Lin, T. Inove, M. L. Miller, O. P. Borella, X. Gen and J. J. Walsh, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 5343.
19. E. Valente, J. R. Gomes, R. Moreira and J. Iley, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2004, **69**, 3359.
20. K. L. Hyeon, J. S. Chun and C. S. Pak, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 3483.
21. A. K. Halve, P. Gour, R. Dubey, D. Bhadauria and B. Bhaskar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2005, **44**, 2163.
22. M. Staudinger, *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1907, **356**, 51.
23. F. P. Cossio, J. M. Ugalde, X. Lopez, B. Lecea and C. Paloma, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 995.
24. Y. Liang, S. J. L. Zhang and J. Xu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2005, **70**, 334.
25. A. K. Halve, P. Gour, R. Dubey, D. Bhadauria and B. Bhaskar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 942.
26. A. W. Bauer, W. M. M. Kirby, J. C. Sherris and M. Turck, *Am. J. Path.*, 1966, **36**, 493.